

101094326 – gEneSys – D7.9

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D. 7.9 – Final data management plan including Protection of Personal Data (POPD)

WP7 – Management and Coordination

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gEneSys (Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems) has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe - Culture, creativity and inclusive society - under grant agreement no. 101094326.

D7.9 – Final Data Management Plan

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Deliverable Information

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<i>WP/Task Responsible</i>	Lucio Pisacane
<i>Keywords</i>	Final data management plan, Protection of Personal Data
<i>Abstract</i>	<p>This document outlines the gEneSys Final Data Management Plan, detailing how data will be managed throughout the project's duration. It covers the following aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the handling of research data during and after the end of the project. • what data will be collected, processed and/or generated. • which methodology and standards will be applied. • whether data will be shared/made open access. • how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project).

Document history

<i>Date</i>	<i>Version</i>	<i>Contributor(s)</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Supervision</i>
31/07/2024	V.01	IRPPS-CNR	First Draft	IRPPS-CNR

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Introduction

As defined in art. 15 of the Grant Agreement and following the principles described in the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon Europe, gEneSys project will ensure open access to all relevant output and to research data: each beneficiary will disseminate its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means, such as scientific publications (an ad-hoc guidelines containing publication policies in gEneSys has been produced, see ANNEX 1), in order to maximise opportunities for future researchers, foster collaborations, greater impacts, etc. This does not change the obligation to protect results, the confidentiality and security in Article 13, or the obligations to protect personal data, all of which still apply.

Having the overall objective to implement research aimed at studying the nexus between gender and energy transition to transform gender interrelations of power in the energy sector, the gEneSys project will draw on both quantitative and qualitative methodologies (specifically in WP1, WP2 and WP3).

Since the start of the project, several desk-based research activities have been successfully completed:

- a systematic literature review on the relationship between gender and energy transition/transformation;
- an ontology of the energy system;
- a gendered assessment of the energy systems knowledge community;
- a gendered assessment of EU Recovery and Resiliency Plans;
- a gendered assessment of Africa-EU cooperation activities in the energy transition sector;
- an analysis of how to incorporate the gender dimension into the SHIFT questions; and
- a series of activities in preparation of the data collection phase.

The project will proceed to the next phase, in fact, gEneSys will undertake various activities that require the collection of personal data. These activities will be further described in the following subsections:

- a multi-country, comparative, gendered assessment survey of stakeholder organizations in sustainable energy systems (WP1);
- a large N (30.000) cross-country citizen survey (WP2);
- up to 60 semi-structured interviews (WP2);
- a Delphi study engaging experts improving their theoretical understanding of the data patterns explored in the citizen survey (WP2);

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- participatory observation of the teams working in the energy sector (WP3); and
- reflexive workshops with female energy researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs and leaders (WP3).

Undertaking these initiatives led to data management challenges that were addressed and resolved. Specifically, the efforts in Africa prompted ethical and data protection issues, temporarily pausing data collection. After an initial ethics review by the EU-appointed expert, we had to seek additional ethical clearance from an external Commission. The CNR Ethics Committee reviewed our human involving activities and personal data collection practices and provided clearance conditional on a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). Further ethics evaluation insisted on a DPIA and contemplation of other factors. Subsequently, a DPIA was drafted, reviewed by the CNR Data Protection Officer, and approved by the Data controller. As per CNR Ethics Committee's requirements, Professor Maria Grasso has been designated as Ethic Mentor to oversee and consult on ethics and data protection for the project.

While some project activities have slowed down and others have been temporarily stopped, the entire process has prompted us to earnestly contemplate the data protection dimensions related to the collection of data.

The gathering of data opens the door for extensive analyses, which can reveal important insights across various sectors and scholarly areas. However, potential new research based on existing data sets is frequently hindered by the lack of standardized and meticulous data curation and documentation. Occasionally, datasets are documented poorly, making it challenging to comprehend their content or the methods of their production. Furthermore, disparate metadata standards among data catalogues and repositories hinder efficient searching and compilation of the data, pointing to the importance of rigorous data management and record-keeping in research endeavours.

The National Research Council of Italy (CNR), as the lead organization, verifies the designation of Dr. Lucio Pisacane, Scientific Coordinator of the gEneSys project, along with his management group, as Data Protection Officers (DPO). Moreover, they will ensure that contact details for the Management Office are accessible to all individuals participating in the research.

Purpose and structure of the document

This document serves to detail the final version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the gEneSys project. The DMP details procedures for handling data during and after the research initiative. Managing research data is a multifaceted issue, owing to the variety of data types, diverse formats, and accessibility hurdles. As such, Horizon Europe requires a DMP for each project, which will describe measures to keep data usable in the long run. A DMP evolves over a project's duration, recording changes to all data sets' life cycles. This document includes information about:

- regulations and indications about Data Management in Horizon Europe;
- which data will be collected, processed, and/or generated, and how; and
- whether data will be shared/made open access and how data will be curated and preserved.

Horizon Europe regulations

Horizon Europe beneficiaries are asked to make their research data [FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSABLE \(FAIR\)](#), to ensure it is soundly managed:

- **Findable:** the created datasets have to be described by sufficiently rich metadata and registered or indexed in a searchable resource. Digital assets should be uniquely identified through the use of Persistent Identifiers that are globally resolvable (PIDs)
- **Accessible:** data sets have to be obtainable by humans and machines upon appropriate authorisation and through a well-defined and universally implementable protocol.
- **Interoperable:** data sets are created in a formal, accessible, shared and broadly applicable format and when a language for knowledge representation is used.
- **Re-usable:** rich metadata and documentation must be provided that follow relevant community standards and provide information on provenance.

The European Commission is running a flexible pilot under Horizon 2020 called the Open Research Data Pilot (ORD pilot). The ORD pilot aimed to improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by Horizon 2020 projects. It takes into account the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR),

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privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions. From the 2017 work programme, the Open Research Data pilot has been extended now to cover all the thematic areas of Horizon 2020 and now in Horizon Europe.

This general principle has become even more important after the pandemic period. Making all research publications and research findings immediately available; making research data openly accessible; providing open access to all data that may be useful to researchers have become key factors in a time when transfers among places are harder and in person access to information is reduced.

Data Summary

gEneSys will collect and use two types of data: primary (generated) data and secondary (already existing) data. gEneSys will collect and analyse both primary and secondary data, across WP1, WP2, and WP3.

In particular, as stated in the grant agreement (GA), tasks involved in the collection of primary data are:

T1.1 Systematic literature review to design analytical framework for review of EU and national energy transition-related policy frameworks [PRIMARY DATA] (Months: 1-6)

T1.1 will conduct a systematic literature review on gender studies and sustainable energy systems. The review will cover the policy, economic, environmental, cultural, governance, and technological subsystems of the energy transition ecosystem and adopt the Gendered Innovation perspective.

T1.4. Gendered assessment of EU policies for sustainable energy systems [PRIMARY DATA] (Months 6-13)

This task will perform a comparative policy analysis of the national recovery and resilience plans elaborated by all EU member states to map and compare how the different countries have incorporated provisions concerning the 'green deal', gender equality, and the mission to achieve energy transition. The comparison will pay special attention to how gender equality, diversity, and inclusion have been accounted for and where targeted gender mainstreaming is needed. The analysis will be done through a rigorous and comprehensive text analysis and will cover the economic, environmental, cultural, governance and technological subsystems. The analysis will also explore how policy decisions are made, the expected impact in terms of equity/fairness and the targets of the policies for sustainable energy systems at EU and national level.

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T1.5. Data set: Stakeholder assessment [PRIMARY DATA] (Months 6-15)

The survey will contain detailed questions about women's participation and empowerment in energy transition, specifically collecting workers' opinions on the future of energy sector in terms of: i) professional needs of workers; ii), the relationship between women and the energy sector with regard to gender stereotypes and the skills of women workers; iii) strategies to attract young people to the study of STEM subjects, taking into account obstacles as well as potentials. The survey will involve stakeholder organisations operating in the sector of energy transition in four European countries participating in the project (i.e., Germany, Italy, Poland, United Kingdom) to identify differences and similarities.

T2.1. Intersectional citizen survey [PRIMARY DATA] (Months 7-21)

A service provider will be commissioned to collect a unique data set for the exploration of intersectional patterns within the gender-energy nexus for six EU member states and four sub-Saharan countries. A total of 30,000 citizens of the 10 target countries are surveyed about their experiences of marginalisation in connection with energy consumption and energy policy. The questions include income, self-assessment of health status, self-assessment as part of a discriminated group and a range of political orientations. Within the framework of this task, the data collection process will be coordinated with a commissioned survey provider, the field phase will be guided by gEneSys, including how the data are collected and processed for analysis.

T2.2 Data set: Delphi survey [PRIMARY DATA] (Months: 15-21)

The dataset collected in T2.1 will be exploratively analysed for intersectional patterns of marginalisation related to energy consumption and energy policy within the ten target countries. A Delphi survey will be organized with a group of 10-15 experts for the co-creation process that will be identified by reputational sampling within the Advisory board and beyond. The expert panel members read the exploratory data report, and then answer a series of questions about it aimed at improving the theoretical understanding of the explored data patterns.

T2.3 Citizen interview transcripts [PRIMARY DATA] (Months 14-26)

Approximately 45-minute-long interviews will be conducted by the same service provider who conducted the data collection in T2.1 with up to 60 individuals using a maximum of 10 interview guidelines provided by the research team. The service provider supplies the research team with translated interview transcripts for analysis. The interview partners will be determined based on the data set collected, and in

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coordination with WP1 and WP3. The interview data are used to compile case studies with the aim to substantiate the intersectional data patterns and their theoretical explanations elaborated in the course of T2.1 and T2.2.

T3.2 Analyse and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the fossil fuel-based vs. the renewable energy systems [PRIMARY DATA] (Months 8-24)

T3.2 will use participatory and co-creation approaches involving university students and teachers to provide new insights and practical solutions to help universities revise their pedagogies and career advice by paying attention to the values of inclusion, sustainability, justice, and fairness when promoting skills and careers for the 'green new deal' panorama or jobs and careers.

T3.3 Increase the participation of women in energy systems and in advancing energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders [PRIMARY DATA] (Months 24-32)

To design a long-term impact on the energy landscape, T3.3 will employ participatory and reflexive national workshops involving female researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders. Building on the findings of T3.2 and T3.3, an international masterclass on pedagogy and training, focusing on gender aspects of energy transition, will be developed. Collaborating with WP4, T3.2 will create an information pack to assist the African Institute of Mathematical Sciences in attracting more women to their researcher training programs.

On the contrary, secondary data will be collected and used in the following tasks:

T1.3 Gendered assessment of energy-systems-knowledge-community [SECONDARY DATA] (Months 8-13)

Once the energy system domain is defined, WP1 will retrieve evidence on the corresponding research communities from the SCOPUS database. This community will be analysed as a social network constructed with the help of innovative gendered assessment techniques, using novel indicators, such as network centrality and semantic centrality of researchers.

T2.3 Case study analyses [SECONDARY] (Months 14-26)

The aim of this task is to test the applicability of the theoretical framework developed in T2.2. to concrete cases of energy transformation and to further improve the derived theoretical framework. The case studies are based on the data collected in the citizen survey and the interviews with citizens and may also include further

literature research and external data sets.

1. Re-use of existing data

In Task 1.3 and Task 2.3, we will utilize available secondary data. For Task 1.3, the use of pre-existing datasets is essential to achieve our objectives. We will obtain data from the SCOPUS database which will be instrumental in conducting a gender-specific evaluation of the energy systems knowledge community. As for Task 2.3, data acquired from various entities such as the World Bank, ILO, UN, OECD might be used to augment the primary data collected in Tasks 2.1 and 2.2, thus facilitating a more detailed and comprehensive analysis.

2. Types and formats of data

gEneSys will generate and re-use several types of qualitative and quantitative data in different formats. Data collected and re-used will include survey data, interviews, transcripts, notes, and coded texts. All the data will be converted from proprietary formats (such as SPSS, STATA) and made available in open well-known and documented formats (such as R, CSV) to allow accessibility and reusability.

3. Expected size of the data

Currently, we are unable to provide a precise figure for the volume of data; however, we can offer an approximation that may be subject to revisions upon the completion of the data-gathering phase. The preliminary data is expected to include roughly 200 questionnaires for Task 1.5, around 30,000 questionnaires for Task 2.1, 15 Delphi Surveys for Task 2.2, transcripts from 60 interviews, each lasting 45 minutes, for Task 2.3, and the participation of 60 individuals in co-creation activities for Task 3.2. In addition, data have been compiled from 152 publications for Task 1.1.

With regard to secondary data, gEneSys has collated information from approximately 18,000 publications for Task 1.3. At this time, the quantity of secondary data to be repurposed for Task 2.3 remains undetermined.

4. Origin/provenance of the data

The data will be collected from several different sources. Table 1 reports the source from which data will be collected within each task.

Task Number	Type of Data	Data Source
T1.1	Primary	Qualitative and quantitative data have been extracted

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		from 152 publications from the Web of Science Database.
T1.3	Primary	Qualitative and quantitative Data have been extracted for about 18,000 publications from the SCOPUS Database
T1.4	Primary	Qualitative and quantitative data have been extracted from all EU countries recovery and resiliency plans
T1.5	Primary	Quantitative data will be collected through a survey administered to researchers working on energy transition related fields in private and public research institutions and universities. We estimate about 200 respondents.
T2.1	Primary	Quantitative data will be collected through a survey administered in six EU countries and four African countries, to about 30,000 country representative respondents. The survey administration has been sub-contracted by Fraunhofer to Ipsos.
T2.2	Primary	Qualitative data will be collected among a group of about 60 experts through a Delphi survey.
T2.3	Primary and Secondary	Primary data will be collected through interviews conducted in six EU countries and four African countries and involving about 60 citizens selected among the participants in the survey of T2.1. The interviews have been sub-contracted by Fraunhofer to Ipsos. Secondary data might be collected from different sources, but at this stage we cannot provide a complete list of sources nor an estimate of the amount of data that will be collected. As an example, data can be collected from Worl Bank, ILO, UN, OECD databases.
T3.2	Primary	Qualitative data will be collected in workshops involving university students.
T3.3	Primary	Qualitative data will be collected in workshops involving female researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders.

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5. Data utility outside the gEneSys project?

The data generated by the gEneSys project will benefit various stakeholders. Primarily, it will aid the research community focused on sustainability/green energy and interplay between energy transition and gender to build upon the Project's analyses or to conduct new studies. Furthermore, this data can support public authorities in creating policies that are more data driven and informed.

The gEneSys project ensures its datasets are accessible to researchers and other interested parties, especially through webinars (WP7). Specifically, about 50 experts with a background in social sciences and quantitative analysis from sub-Saharan Africa will be identified. These experts will be introduced to the citizen survey dataset during a webinar and will learn how to utilize it. This action will further maximize the dissemination of the collected data.

FAIR data

1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The datasets generated by gEneSys will be accessible via a dedicated community page on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/genesys/>). Each dataset will be assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). They will include a codebook (ANNEX 1) detailing the variables and collection or production methodology, along with a README file containing pertinent details (ANNEX 1).

Adhering to the FAIR principles, we will also furnish the necessary metadata for every database generated by gEneSys:

- DOI
- Publication date
- Creator/s names and affiliations
- Abstract with the specification of the project deliverable to which pertains
- Licence type
- Contributors' names and affiliations
- Keywords
- Language
- Version number
- Related works
- Funding
- Reference – how to cite
- Domain specific field

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Metadata will be directly compiled on Zenodo at the moment the database is uploaded, and this will allow metadata to be harvested and indexed by the search engines.

2. Making data accessible

In line with GDPR rules, we will not release any personal data that can identify individuals; however, we will share anonymized, aggregate data on Zenodo for public access. Zenodo ensures our datasets receive a DOI and are accompanied by appropriate metadata, promoting maximum accessibility. There will be no hold on the dataset availability. Anyone can use the data without restrictions during or post-project if they properly cite it as specified. Metadata will be generated to aid in finding and recognizing the datasets.

We will ensure data uniformity, comparability, and reliability through collaboration among partners. Project leaders will enforce standards to maintain high-quality and accurate data, which entails training those gathering data, as well as monitoring and validating data handling and analysis processes. Metadata and documentation associated with the datasets will also be under a Creative Commons license and will be accessible indefinitely.

3. Other research output and allocation of resources

The gEneSys Project will yield various outputs including data, scientific articles, policy briefs, and other deliverables. Except for scientific papers, all products will be accessible on the gEneSys Zenodo Community platform. Scientific papers will appear in open access or hybrid journals, utilizing transformative contracts from authors' affiliations for article charge payments, when possible, otherwise project funds will cover these costs. Currently, the expense for open access publications is undetermined as they depend on the number of publications and their destinations.

4. Ethics and Data Security

The gEneSys project's primary potential hazards include unauthorized revelation of respondent, interviewee, and expert consultant identities, as well as inadequate security for private sensitive data that might expose individuals to discrimination or stigma due to their political beliefs or health status. Therefore, ensuring confidentiality and implementing proper procedures for managing, processing, and storing this information will be a key focus throughout the research process and afterwards.

The right to data protection is guaranteed by the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights

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and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union. It gives effect to the right to privacy by providing individuals with autonomy and control over the way their information is collected and used. In research settings, data protection creates obligations on researchers to provide research subjects with detailed information about what will happen to the personal data that they collect from them and to comply to this information. Especially, it requires all data processing entities to ensure the data is properly protected, 'minimised', and destroyed when no longer needed.

As every EU-funded research project that processes personal data, also gEneSys will comply with: EU and national data protection laws, ethical considerations and the values and principles underpinning the EU.

Data collected via recording (audio and video files) will be immediately downloaded from the recorder system on return to the researcher's office in a secure directory or secure file server. Information on the recorder is deleted directly afterwards. For the process of transcribing qualitative interviews, transcribers will follow strict confidentiality and data security protocols. Individual information on interviewees (such as names, nationalities, age, legal conditions) will be gathered but will be stored following principles of strictest confidentiality separately from the remaining collected information so that no information can be directly linked to the person of the respondent. Personal data collected will be used to create an alphanumeric code, that will guarantee anonymisation of participants and will be used during the research and later.

Data that can identify individuals will not be published or made available or passed on to third parties. The real name of each interviewee will be substituted by an alias. Same applies to other distinguishing personal information that will be replaced with a pseudonym. To any interviewee access to a copy of the anonymized personal interview will be granted upon request. The signed informed sheets are stored in a protected environment and separated from the remaining collected information so that no information can be directly linked to the person of the respondent.

All primary and secondary data collected by the gEneSys project will be securely stored on dedicated computers or file servers located at each data-collecting partner's premises. To ensure the security of the data, appropriate measures such as firewalls and password protection will be implemented on the computers and networks

Data access must be restricted to authorised researchers of the project that will sign a data protection statement for the specific data set. Researchers will not be allowed to keep copies of the data sets beyond the agreed time window for data analyses or allow others to access the data sets.

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For a deeper and comprehensive discussion on ethics and data security in gEneSys project, please refer to the Deliverable 8.1 and the DPIA attached to it and, generally, to WP 8 on Ethics Requirements.

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ANNEX 1 Guidelines for gEneSys Publications

Introduction

As mentioned in the Deliverable 7.9 – Final Data Management Plan, the present document describes the policy to be followed for the publications of the outputs produced by the gEneSys Project. In the following sections, we will describe the policies to be implemented for the publications of Deliverables and other reports, Datasets and Scientific Publications.

Deliverable and other reports

Deliverables and other reports will be published on the Zenodo gEneSys Community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/genesys/>), as soon as they are delivered to the EC.

Deliverables and other reports will be uploaded on Zenodo with the following metadata:

- Publication date
- Creator/s names and affiliations
- Abstract with the specification of the Project deliverable to which pertains
- Licence type
- Contributors' names and affiliations
- Keywords
- Language
- Version number
- Funding
- Reference – how to cite
- Domain specific field

The Deliverables and other reports can be uploaded directly by the WP leader or its collaborators, and the metadata directly compiled. In alternative, WP leaders can ask the Project coordinator to upload the document with all relevant metadata.

Scientific Publications

In principle, scientific publications will be published open access (OA) in OA or Hybrid journals. To minimize the cost of OA publishing for the gEneSys Project, firstly transformative contracts signed by authors' institutions will be consulted. If no transformative contract is available, the Article processing charge (APC) will be paid with gEneSys dedicated funds by the leading author's institution.

To ensure value for money, if more than a potential journal is identified for publishing, *ceteris paribus*, authors should prefer the one with which a transformative contract exist or the one with the lowest APC.

To promote gender equality in publishing, if more than a potential journal is identified for publishing, *ceteris paribus*, authors should prefer the journal in which there is the highest level of gender equality among the editorial board.

To maximize the early dissemination of the scientific publications, if more than a potential journal is identified for publishing, *ceteris paribus*, authors should prefer the journal that allow the publication of the pre-print pre-peer reviewed version of the paper and publish it in the gEneSys Zenodo Community.

Datasets

Datasets will be published open access and freely accessible to all on the gEneSys Zenodo Community. To guaranty the applications of the FAIR principles, each dataset will be published with a codebook containing the list and description of the variables and the methodology employed to collect, clean, and recode the data, and a README file with relevant information (see subsections below). The dataset will be published in non-proprietary and proprietary widely employed data formats (such as CSV, R, Excel, SPSS, STATA).

Each dataset will be uploaded to Zenodo alongside all the relevant metadata:

- Publication date
- Creator/s names and affiliations
- Abstract with the specification of the Project deliverable to which pertains
- Licence type
- Contributors' names and affiliations
- Keywords
- Language

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- Version number
- Related works
- Funding
- Reference – how to cite
- Domain specific field

Codebook and data documentation Template

This represents the minimum standard that will be followed. Therefore, dataset documentation will be adapted depending on the dataset in line with international standards where these exist.

The codebook and data documentation should report the following sections

1. Abstract
2. Material and methods
3. Codebook

The codebook should be formatted as table 1.

Table 1 reports the dataset's codebook with the variables name, variables type and variables description.

Variable name	Variable type	Variable description
Variable name as reported in the dataset labels	Numerical, Textual, Alphanumeric etc.	Description of the variable

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README file

The readme file should be placed in the folder along the different formats of the dataset, and the Codebook and data documentation file. The README file should have the following structure:

Dataset Title:

gEneSys Project_wpXXX_tXXX_Dataset Title_Name of the data curator_Version number

Description:

Add a description of the dataset

Dataset Information:

Version: XXX (Publication date)

Author: Name and surname

Maintainer: Name and surname (Email, affiliation)

Date of Collection: XXX

Data Dictionary:

See the file "Documentation and Codebook of the Dataset – DATASET TITLE"

Contents of the folder:

LIST EVERY FILE CONTAINED IN THE FOLDER WITH A BRIEF EXPLANATION, for instance:

1. "Documentation and Codebook of the Dataset – DATASET TITLE" - Report the method of data collection and the variable codebook and descriptions.
2. "DATASET TITLE.dta" - Dataset in STATA format
3. " DATASET TITLE.RData" - Dataset in R format
4. " DATASET TITLE.rds" - Dataset in R format
5. " DATASET TITLE.sav" - Dataset in SPSS format
6. " DATASET TITLE.csv" - Data in CSV format
7. " DATASET TITLE.xlsx - Data in EXCEL format

Instructions on how to use the dataset:

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D7.9 – Final Data Management Plan

Open the file with the appropriate software. For details on methods and variables, see the file "Documentation and Codebook of the Dataset – DATASET TITLE".

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D7.9 – Final Data Management Plan

List of Acronyms

APC: Article Processing Charge

CNR: Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

DMP: Data Management Plan

DOI: Digital Object Identifier

DPIA: Data Protection Impact Assessment

DPO: Data Protection Officer

EU: European Union

FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable

GA: Grant Agreement

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

ILO: International Labour Organization

IPR: Intellectual Property Rights

OA: Open Access

OECD: Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development

ORD: Open Research Data

UN: United Nations

WP: Work Package